

Ectopic Molar Tubal Pregnancy: An Important Histological Presentation

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Ectopic localization of molar pregnancy is rare from review of literature. To date, only 132 cases have been reported. The identification of molar pregnancies in this setting is critical given their malignant potential and post-surgical management. We present a case of tubal hydatiform molar pregnancy with features suggestive of partial mole, detailing the patient's initial presentation, explorative surgical evaluation, and finally the revelation of diagnosis based upon pathological determination. It is essential for providers to not only be informed of an unusual pathology but of the importance and value of histological examination of tubal specimens post-surgery with the pertinence to diagnose cases of molar pregnancy for prompt and appropriate post-operative surveillance.

KEYWORDS Ectopic pregnancy; Molar Pregnancy; Gynecology; Gynecological Malignancy; Laparoscopy

Introduction

The incidence of ectopic pregnancy is approximately 20 in 1,000 pregnancies [2]. Hydatidiform molar pregnancies are more rare, occurring approximately 1 in 500 for partial moles and 1 in 1,000 for complete molar pregnancies [2]. Molar pregnancy is a type of gestational trophoblastic disease (GTD). GTD is a group of diseases that are characterized by the abnormal cellular proliferation of trophoblastic cells.

Hydatidiform molar pregnancies are considered pre-malignant and are the consequence of abnormal gametogenesis and fertilization [3]. These are classified based upon genotype; either a partial mole, which typically yield a genotype of 69, XXY or as a complete mole with genotypes 46, XX most commonly. Partial moles have a low risk for developing malignant sequela, approximately 0.5-5 percent. Complete moles, which occur more commonly, carry a 15-20% risk for development of malignant GTD such as invasive mole or choriocarcinoma. [4]. Both require post-surgical surveillance to assess risk and

need for further management. Other than genotypic analysis for definitive diagnosis, the molar pregnancy may be elucidated upon histological findings. These criteria include circumferential trophoblastic proliferation, hydropic scalloped villi, decidualized tissue, myxomatous and karyorrhexis effects of stroma, and avascular cisternae [1]. Once diagnosed, close surveillance with serial beta-human chorionic gonadotropic hormone (β -hCG) is required to assess for malignant potential. Diagnosis is critical for both management and patient counselling.

Case report

A 25-year-old gravida 4, para 2012 with a history of two prior cesarean sections at six weeks + six days by LMP initially presented to ER with resolved lower abdominal pain and non-bloody vaginal discharge. At that time, the patient had a positive β -hCG (387 mIU/mL) with no intrauterine pregnancy and a thickened endometrium of 3 cm on pelvic ultrasound. Otherwise, the patient was asymptomatic with unremarkable vitals and labs. As this was a desired pregnancy, the patient underwent serial surveillance β -hCG levels and follow-up imaging for the pregnancy of unknown location. On subsequent assessment in the emergency setting, the patient demonstrated abdominal tenderness with palpation and noted to have scant vaginal bleeding with transvaginal ultrasound (TVUS). Official Transabdominal and TVUS demonstrated a left ovarian hemorrhagic structure, no IUP, no evidence of ectopic gestation, and no evidence of free fluid [Figure 1]. Bedside TVUS revealed a left cystic ovarian struc-

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ture with septations, no IUP, thickened endometrial stripe of 1.8 cm, and minimal free fluid in the posterior cul-de-sac. β -hCG was rising inappropriately with values shown in Table 1. The patient was diagnosed with possible ectopic pregnancy vs miscarriage (secondarily to the thickness of endometrium) and was taken to the operating room for Dilatation and Curettage (D&C) with possible diagnostic laparoscopy and salpingectomy. After D&C, uterine contents were assessed intra-operatively revealing no gestational sac or chorionic villi. Diagnostic laparoscopy was performed which demonstrated scant hemoperitoneum, extensive adhesive disease, and enlarged cystic ovary that was plastered to the side wall. Once adhesions were lysed, a left enlarged fallopian tube suspicious for ectopic pregnancy [Figure 2] was visualized. Left salpingectomy was performed and specimen removed without complications. The D&C specimen and left ectopic pregnancy were sent for pathological review.

Table 1 β -hCG Values

Date	Value (mIU/mL)
9/19/18	387
9/21/18	960
9/23/18	1428
9/25/18	2252
9/27/18	3483
9/29/18	5085

The final pathology of endometrial curettings demonstrated decidualized late secretory endometrium. More interestingly, for the left fallopian tube ectopic specimen, the report revealed circumferential trophoblastic proliferation, decidua, scalloped chorionic villi, myxomatous stroma and avascular cisternae formation consistent with partial hydatidiform molar pregnancy [Figure 3-6]. On the postoperative course, the patient was appraised of pathological findings and serum β -hCG drawn, with a decrease in level noted two weeks post-op to 9 mIU/mL then four weeks later <2 mIU/mL with confirmatory negative urine β -hCG.

Discussion

Clinically, an ectopic molar pregnancy presents similarly to non-GTD pregnancies when found in the fallopian tube. Thus final diagnosis is reached only with pathological evaluation. Histological evaluation is crucial to ensure that appropriate postoperative surveillance can be performed for the patient if a molar pregnancy is diagnosed, i.e. serum β -hCG is followed. Burton et al. have reported that partial hydatidiform mole located in the fallopian tube is a rare occurrence, which can be mistakenly overdiagnosed. Thus pathological specimen should be evaluated appropriately and have the appropriate histological findings to ensure proper diagnosis [5]. This overdiagnosis is secondary to the morphological overlap of early tubal pregnancy and with an ectopic molar, and strict histopathological criteria must be used to ensure accuracy. This currently includes hydrophilic villi, with avascular cisternae, and abnormal trophoblastic proliferation that is circumferential in nature [1]. Identification of molar pregnancies may also be illuminated via imaging (snow-storm, bunch of grapes) have been demonstrated in the adnexal mass

Figure 1: Radiological imaging of uterus and left ovary/adnexa. Figure 1A demonstrates the transabdominal ultrasound of sagittal view of uterus with endometrial strip thickness of 1.8 cm. Figure 1B demonstrates the transvaginal ultrasound of the left ovary with no visualization of the left adnexa. Of note is the heterogeneously hypoechoic structure likely a hemorrhagic cyst which measures 3.50 cm x 3.22 x 2.62 cm.

Figure 2: Laparoscopic findings of tubal ectopic pregnancy as denoted intra-operatively. Ectopic denoted as EP.

of tubal ectopic [6]. In the case presented, the patient's history of prior abdominal surgery created an extensive adhesive disease that was only seen intraoperatively.

The ovary was enlarged secondarily to the cyst and had scarred over the tube; this may have led to the failure to reveal a definitive adnexa structure with imaging studies. Once surgery confirmed the ectopic pregnancy, the final diagnosis of molar pregnancy was elucidated only with a pathological review of tissue. The hydatidiform mole was not considered a differential in the patient's assessment; as the patient was asymptomatic, had a low β -hCG, nor demonstrated ultrasound findings suspicious for a molar pregnancy. Review of literature has suggested that implantation in the fallopian tube may preclude vascularization of the abnormal pregnancy, leading to an uncharacteristically low β -hCG in these molar pregnancies [7]. This explanation can lead to a challenge inaccurate disease pathology. For early desired pregnancies that require consistent surveillance of β -hCG; this can further broaden the differential in cases which the hormone does not rise appropriately as seen in miscarriage. Recognizing tubal molar pregnancies can aid in post-surgical management and follow-up. The diagnosis can assist in counselling patients regarding management and risk for future pregnancies. Literature shows that prior molar preg-

Figure 3: Demonstrate the histopathology of the ectopic specimen with hematoxylin-eosin staining with features characteristic of hydatidiform molar pregnancy. Fig. 3 reveals the myxogenous stroma with hydropic decidua. Fig 4 reveals the circumferential trophoblastic proliferation in the upper left corner of slide. Fig. 5 shows scalloped chorionic villi and characteristic trophoblasts. Fig 6. shows multiple avascular cysternae. Findings of the pathology are characteristic of partial hydatidiform mole.

nancy increases the patient's risk for future molar pregnancies (1-2% for the second molar pregnancy and up to 25% for third molar pregnancy) [8]. By familiarizing oneself regarding tubal molar pregnancies and understanding their presentation and sequela, derangements in serial β -hCG post salpingectomy for ectopic pregnancy could help to illicit ectopic molar pregnancy as a differential. With this report, we wish to educate clinicians in this case on the histological importance of confirmation of hydatidiform mole in an association with ectopic fallopian pregnancy. We also emphasize the challenge which can be presented when imaging fails to ascertain an ectopic pregnancy based upon patient factors such as adhesions, and the uncharacteristic nature of serum β -hCG in ectopic molar pregnancy. Finally, we stress the importance of including ectopic molar pregnancy as a differential in suspected ectopic pregnancies, especially with post-surgical derangements in β -hCG following salpingectomy for an ectopic pregnancy.

Patient consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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